

ВСЕ НАУКИ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ НАУЧНЫЙ

ЖУРНАЛ

№9, 2024

*«ПОЧЕМУ?» – ЭТО ВОПРОС О КОТОРЫЙ ДО СИХ ПОР
РАЗБИВАЛАСЬ ВСЯ ЛОГИКА, ВСЯ ФИЛОСОФИЯ, ВСЯ НАУКА.*

ЭРИХ МАРИЯ РЕМАРК

**НАУЧНО-ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКИЙ ИНСТИТУТ «ФИЗИКИ
РЕЗОНАНСНЫХ ЯДЕРНЫХ РЕАКЦИЙ» ЯВЛЯЕТСЯ НАУЧНЫМ
УЧРЕЖДЕНИЕМ, ОСУЩЕСТВЛЯЮЩИМ
ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫЕ, ПРИКЛАДНЫЕ НАУЧНЫЕ
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ РАЗРАБОТКИ В
ОБЛАСТИ НАУКИ, ТЕХНИКИ, КУЛЬТУРЫ И ПРОСВЕЩЕНИЯ.**

Все науки. №9, 2024

Международный научный
журнал

Издательские решения
По лицензии Ridero
2024

CHARACTERISTIC MANIFESTATION OF SPIRITUALITY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF IDEOLOGICAL FACTORS

UDK: 101.8

Ilyasov Shakhrukh Burkhanovich

Graduate student of Chirchik State Pedagogical University

Annotation. The article analyzes the importance of spirituality in the development of Uzbekistan in the new stage of development and its connection with the idea, the development of ideological factors.

Key words: thought, idea, ideology, spirituality, virtue, strong civil society, public control, social personality, national spirit, high spirituality.

A person cannot rise without spirituality, society cannot develop without spirituality. Every nation and people try to raise and develop their national spirituality based on their nationality. As for why, the experience of mankind for thousands of years shows that «if the violent and aggressive forces in the world want to subjugate and subjugate any nation or country and take possession of its wealth, first of all, they must disarm it, or tries to separate it from its greatest wealth, its national values, history and spirituality.

The history of national spirituality is related to the process of spiritual development of the nation, in which sometimes centuries can be equal to days, and days can be equal to centuries. One thing is clear for the historical process of mankind: historical events, persons, events pass away, elements of material culture decay, but spirituality grows, becomes richer, and acquires a wider scope and deeper content. No nation lives alone in the world, nor does it develop in isolation. Peoples and nations always interact with each other in different ways and influence each other throughout history, enriching themselves and others spiritually. But no nation has ever been able to get rid of its identity and enrich itself at the expense of the spirituality of another nation.

Today we are living in the age of conflict of spirituality and cultures in the 21st century. We are living in a time when some people are trying to introduce cultures that are contrary to the nationalities of peoples, calling them mass culture. It can be said that we live in very difficult times. Our president Shavkat Mirziyoyev put forward the following opinion about this: «In the ever-increasing world, geo-political and geo-economic contradictions are intensifying, the desire to resolve conflicts and conflicts arising in the system of international relations by force is increasing. The powerful centers, which used to protect their goals and interests mainly through diplomacy and politics, have now turned to open pressure, confrontation and conflict, witnessing the increasing tension and conflicts. we are being». As a result of this, in my opinion, the need of all peoples and countries in the world for the issue of spirituality is increasing. Because in such a dangerous time, only a highly moral and united people can survive. The need for universal spirituality is increasing in the world.

Universal spirituality — spiritual phenomena, cultural assets, literature, science, art achievements, religion, politics is a concept in the understanding of results in the field of law. The essence of universal spirituality is explained in detail with examples and evidence in President Islam Karimov's work «High spirituality — invincible power».

The phenomenon of spirituality mainly manifests itself in two forms: the spirituality of an individual and the spirituality of a nation. Spirituality is a ray of light from the mirror of the soul, it is hidden in the human heart. Therefore, it seems necessary that the study of spirituality begins with the study of the spirituality of the individual. In fact, the spiritual world of each person is a world without its own territory. But each person lives in a certain society, a certain group of people, belongs to a certain nation. Naturally, as each individual person grows up, he is influenced by the people living in his environment. The spiritual maturity of a person begins with the influence of this environment. Every person, regardless of whether he understands it deeply or not, cannot help but belong to a nation or a nation, no person lives completely apart from the nation. According to the saying of the first President, «each person feels that he is a part of his nation, only when he thinks about it, works hard and lives with spirituality.»

This means that the spirituality of an individual is in reality not separate from the spirituality of the nation. Therefore, it is impossible to study the spirituality of an individual without having a certain idea about the spirituality of the nation. Although, historically and theoretically, the spirituality of a nation literally consists of the sum of the spirituality of all past, present and future individuals who are considered to be related to this nation in some way, but in reality each person is its spirit is nourished by the spirituality of the nation, it matures on the basis of it.

Some people claim that in the conditions of a free market economy, the value of spiritual, educational and moral values decreases, culture and

spirituality become secondary, and spiritual poverty increases. In my opinion, such a contrast between free market economy and spirituality is completely inappropriate. In fact, as noted above, they complement each other, because only a spiritually healthy, strong society can implement reforms.

But unfortunately, the scourge of corruption is attacking the reforms being carried out to improve the society. «According to the analysis, the world economy is currently suffering losses in the amount of 3 trillion US dollars annually due to corruption. However, these are approximate calculations and cannot fully represent the exact size of economic losses. The most important thing is that the extent of the moral damage it causes to the society cannot be measured by any criteria. This is a sad situation in my opinion. As a result, the reforms in society are not having the intended effect. And the people's living conditions are becoming difficult or slow to improve.

On the issue of corruption, our president Shavkat Mirziyoyev put forward the following opinion: "...fighting against corruption is the sacred duty of every conscientious person, democratic society and state. It is of urgent importance to form a culture of intolerance to corruption and true respect for the Constitution and laws in society.» We will achieve our goals only if we take these rules as our principles in all our work. If people can get rid of the scourge of corruption, the development of the society will definitely increase rapidly.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Karimov I.A. High spirituality — invincible power — T.: Ma'naviyat, 2008. — P. 11
2. Mirziyoyev Sh. Modern and new Uzbekistan — T: Uzbekistan, 2024 — B 16 —17
3. Karimov I.A. Uzbekistan: national independence, economy, political ideology — T: Uzbekistan, 1996. -B 81
4. Mirziyoyev SH. Modern and New Uzbekistan — T: Uzbekistan, 2024 — B 25
5. Mirziyoyev SH. Modern and New Uzbekistan — T: Uzbekistan, 2024 — B 25

CHARACTERISTIC MANIFESTATION OF SPIRITUALITY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF IDEOLOGICAL FACTORS	74
Ilyasov Shakhrukh Burkhanovich	74
Graduate student of Chirchik State Pedagogical University	74
LIST OF REFERENCES	76
YOSHLAR MA'NAVIY-AXLOQIY TARBIYASIDA JADID MA'RIFATPARVARLARINING O'RNI	77
UDK: 129	77
Quldosheva Shahrizoda Nurali qizi	77
CHDPU, Gumanitar fanlar fakulteti talabasi	77
Adabiyotlar ro'yxati	81
TECHNOLOGIES FOR FORMING STUDENTS» SOCIALLY ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP COMPETENCE	83
Ikramov Farkhod Aktamovich	83
CHDPU researcher	83
REFERENCES	87
THE ROLE OF EDUCATION IN ENHANCING THE SPIRITUALITY OF WOMEN	90
Sabriddinova Kibriyo	90
Chirchik State Pedagogical University Faculty of Humanities 2nd year student	90
References	93
ФИЛОСОФСКИЕ НАУКИ	95
FROM THE INFORMATION SOCIETY TO THE DIGITAL SOCIETY: A COMPRATIVIST ANALYSIS	97
GAFFAROVA Gulchehra Ghulamzhanovna	97
Faculty of Humanities, Chirchik State Pedagogical University	97
Head of the Department of National Idea, Fundamentals of Spirituality and Legal Education, prof	97
Conclusion	105
REFERENCES	109
PROGRESS AND IMPLICATIONS OF PROPAGANDA IN CYBERSPACE	112
Berkinov Oybek Tokhir o'g'li, Teacher of Chirchik State Pedagogical University	112
ORCID 0009-0000-9467-6201, e-mail: oybekberkinov98@gmail.com ...	112
Bibliographic list	117

Ибратжон Хатамович Алиев
Дониёр Давронбекович Ибрагимов
Султонали Мукарамович Абдурахмонов
Голибжон Оббозжонович Кулдашов
Жамолитдин Солижанович Абдуллаев
Сувонкул Эрханович Нурманов
Юлдош Юсуфбоевич Якубов
Жохонгир Анваржонович Иброхимов
Фарход Актамович Икрамов
Шахруҳ Бурҳанович Илясов
Шахризода Нурали қизи Қулдошева
Кибриё Сабриддинова
Гулчехра Гуламжановна Гаффарова
Ойбек Тоҳир ўғли Беркинов

Все науки. №9, 2024
Международный научный журнал

Главный редактор Ибратжон Хатамович Алиев
Редактор Миродилжон Хомуджонович Баратов
Редактор Гулчехра Гуламжановна Гаффарова
Иллюстратор Фарходжон Анваржонович Иброхимов
Дизайнер обложки Раънохон Мукарамовна Алиева
Дизайнер обложки Ибратжон Хатамович Алиев
Технический директор Султонали Мукарамович Абдурахмонов
Экономический директор Ботирали Рустамович Жалолов
Корректор Гулноза Мухтаровна Собирова
Корректор Дилноза Орзиқуловна Норбоева
Модератор Фарходжон Анваржонович Иброхимов

Авторами научных публикаций являются академики, доктора и кандидаты наук, профессора, доценты, преподаватели, сотрудники, магистры, студенты и иные самостоятельные исследователи. Каждый из них активно проводит научные исследования в разных областях науки и техники, представляя в качестве результатов проведённых работ научные статьи.

Международный научный журнал «Все науки», созданный при ООО «Electron Laboratory» и Научной школе «Электрон», является научным изданием, публикующим последние научные результаты в самых различных областях точных, естественных, гуманитарных и других наук, техники, представляя собой также сборник публикаций по вышеуказанным темам коллегии авторов, рецензируемый редколлегией редакции журнала и учёным советом НИИ «ФРЯР» при Electron Laboratory LLC ежемесячно.

Rideró

Rideró.ru — издай
книгу бесплатно!